

Model of Multicultural Education Practices for Students in Higher Education

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 08,2026</p> <p>Accepted: May 10,2026</p> <p>Keywords : Multicultural Education Practices, Equal Opportunities, Equal Toleranceculture</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20111934</p>	<p><i>This research aims to offer multicultural education practices model. Questionnaires were distributed to 322 students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta taken by simple random sampling. Analysis of Structural Equation Modeling suggests that multicultural education practices is predicted by campus climate and hidden curriculum, teaching styles and strategies, communication language, and elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students. Indicator of campus climate and hidden curriculum ensuring equal opportunities for all students is stimulated by equality of teacher behaviour, equal tolerance culture, and equal opportunities given to all students related to participation in classroom. Indicator of teaching styles and strategies ensuring equal opportunities for all students is supported by sub-indicators of equal opportunities for all students to give opinions, to ask questions, and to show their competences. Indicator of language of communication ensuring equal opportunities for all students is influenced by sub-indicators of equal opportunities for all students to use their own regional language of communication in free time, code of conduct applying to all students to appreciate the respective regional languages, and equal opportunities for all students to use international language in teaching and learning process. Indicator of elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students is promoted by sub-indicators of equal opportunities for all students to join the school program, to participate in class discussion, and to give recommendation for campus. The research concluded that a model of multicultural education practices proposed in this research can be applied for higher education students.</i></p>

Introduction

Multiculturalism is very important in facing the problems in globalization era. Many studies discussed about multiculturalism. Multiculturalism is done to provide equal opportunity to all students having different ethnic backgrounds (Omar, Noh, Hamzah, & Majid, 2015). The teachers is recommended to apply the methods suitable with various culture of the students in the process of learning in order to promote optimal interaction. Content of multicultural should be integrated in the practices of teachers especially in the diverse society (Brown & Livstrom, 2020; Freire & Valdez, 2021). The dimensions of multicultural education are comprised of integration of content, construction of knowledge, reduction of prejudice, pedagogy of equitable system, and school culture of empowerment. (Quinto-Pozos, Martinez, Suarez, & Zech, 2018; Warshaw, Crume, & Perez, 2020). Multicultural awareness can be heightened by using service-learning experience (Quinto-Pozos, Martinez, Suarez, & Zech, 2018; Warshaw, Crume, & Perez, 2020). This strategy can provide the students chances for *in situ* learning and improve self-esteem, more willingness to take care of others, respect for diversity, and feel more empathy.

Hypothesis of this research is that multicultural education practices is predicted by campus climate and hidden curriculum, teaching styles and strategies, communication language, and elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students (Brown & Livstrom, 2020; Freire & Valdez, 2021). Fig. 1 shows the theoretical framework of this study.

Fig. 1 Theoretical framework of the study

Method

This research objective was to find out the effect of campus climate and hidden curriculum, teaching styles and strategies, communication language, and elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students on multicultural education practices. The survey method was conducted in this research. Data collection in this research utilized questionnaires associated with campus climate and hidden curriculum, teaching styles and strategies, communication language, and elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students as the exogenous variables and multicultural education practices as the endogenous variable in this research. There were 322 students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia replying to the survey.

Content analysis of the literature about multicultural education practices was based on Brown & Livstrom (2020) and Freire & Valdez (2021) stating that the effect of campus climate and hidden curriculum, teaching styles and strategies, communication language, and elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students as predictors. The questionnaire changed these ideals into statements distributed to 322 students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia.

The questions concerning endogenous variables of multicultural education practices are composed of three exogenous variables: campus climate and hidden curriculum, teaching styles and strategies, communication language, and elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students. The exogenous variables of campus climate and hidden curriculum ensuring equal opportunities for all students consist of three indicators including equality of teacher behaviour, equal tolerance culture, and equal opportunities given to all students related to participation in classroom. The exogenous variables of teaching styles and strategies ensuring equal opportunities for all students are equal opportunities for all students to give opinions, to ask questions, and to show their competences. The exogenous variables of language of communication ensuring equal opportunities for all students are equal opportunities for all students to use their own regional language of communication in free time, code of conduct applying to all students to appreciate the respective regional languages, and equal opportunities for all students to use international language in teaching and learning process. The exogenous variables of elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students are equal opportunities for all students to join the school program, to participate in class discussion, and to give recommendation for campus.

This research used analysis technique using Structural Equation Model (SEM) with IBM SPSS Statistics 24 and SPSS AMOS 24 with 2017 Edition to examine the set of relationships between multicultural

education practices and the three indicators of campus climate and hidden curriculum, teaching styles and strategies, communication language, and elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students. Campus climate and hidden curriculum, teaching styles and strategies, communication language, and elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students as the exogenous variable and multicultural education practices as the endogenous variable (Safitri, Umasih, Ibrahim, Sujarwo, Marini, and Wahyudi, 2019; Wibowo, Marini, Safitri, Utami, and Wahyudi, 2019; Fahrurrozi, Safitri, Marini, Wahyudi, 2019; Maksum, Safitri, Ibrahim, Marini, and Wahyudi, 2019; Marini, Safitri, & Muda, 2018; Marini, Zulela, Maksum, Satibi, Yarmi, and Wahyudi, 2019; Kaban, Sakmal, Auliaty, Marini, and Wahyudi, 2019; Safitri, Umasih, Yunaz, Marini, and Wahyudi, 2019; Edwita, Safitri, Maksum, Yunaz, Marini, and Muda, 2019; Maksum, Safitri, Ibrahim, Marini, and Wahyudi, 2020). The research data were entered using excel with item scores on the basis of 322 participant responses applying “strongly agree,” “agree,” “neutral,” “disagree,” and “strongly disagree” (scored 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively, for positive questions and 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, for negative questions).

Results and Discussion

a. Results

Table 1 displays statistical analysis in goodness-of-fit. Table 1 shows the model fit summary as an indicator of the informative model fit consisting of Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI), and Comparative Fit Index (CFI).

Table 1. Model Fit Summary

Model	RMSEA	NFI	IFI	CFI
Default model	,077	,825	,878	,875
Saturated model		1,000	1,000	1,000
Independence model	,190	,000	,000	,000

Table 2 displays the measurement model test showing a direct effect of campus climate and hidden curriculum, teaching styles and strategies, communication language, and elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students on multicultural education practices. Table 2 presents a direct effect of sub-indicators of equality of teacher behaviour, equal tolerance culture, and equal opportunities given to all students related to participation in classroom on campus climate and hidden curriculum ensuring equal opportunities for all students. Table 2 indicates a direct effect of sub-indicators of equal opportunities for all students to give opinions, to ask questions, and to show their competences on teaching styles and strategies ensuring equal opportunities for all students. Table 2 shows a direct effect of sub-indicators of equal opportunities for all students to use their own regional language of communication in free time, code of conduct applying to all students to appreciate the respective regional languages, and equal opportunities for all students to use international language in teaching and learning process on language of communication ensuring equal opportunities for all students. Table 2 shows a direct effect of sub-indicators of equal opportunities for all students to join the school program, to participate in class discussion, and to give recommendation for campus on participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students. Figure 2 can see the structural model.

Table 2. Measurement model test
Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
CC	<---	MLTED	,480	,104	4,609	***	
TS	<---	MLTED	,983	,124	7,930	***	
LC	<---	MLTED	,541	,114	4,763	***	
EP	<---	MLTED	1,000				
ME1	<---	CC	1,000				
ME2	<---	CC	2,155	,451	4,776	***	
ME3	<---	CC	1,875	,397	4,723	***	
ME4	<---	TS	1,000				
ME5	<---	TS	,859	,109	7,854	***	
ME6	<---	TS	,846	,105	8,094	***	
ME7	<---	LC	1,000				
ME8	<---	LC	1,475	,339	4,352	***	
ME9	<---	LC	1,209	,281	4,297	***	

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
ME10	<---	EP	1,000				
ME11	<---	EP	1,076	,109	9,858	***	
ME12	<---	EP	,653	,094	6,929	***	

Standardized Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate
CC	<---	MLTED	,898
TS	<---	MLTED	,879
LC	<---	MLTED	1,002
EP	<---	MLTED	,904
ME1	<---	CC	,325
ME2	<---	CC	,642
ME3	<---	CC	,607
ME4	<---	TS	,681
ME5	<---	TS	,556
ME6	<---	TS	,578
ME7	<---	LC	,317
ME8	<---	LC	,437
ME9	<---	LC	,423
ME10	<---	EP	,677
ME11	<---	EP	,730
ME12	<---	EP	,461

Notes:

- MLTED = Multicultural Education Practices
- CC = Campus climate and hidden curriculum ensuring equal opportunities for all students
- TS = Teaching styles and strategies ensuring equal opportunities for all students
- LC = Language of communication ensuring equal opportunities for all students
- EP = Elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students
- ME1 = Equality of teacher behaviour towards all students
- ME2 = Equal tolerance culture for all students at campus
- ME3 = Equal opportunities given to all students related to participation in classroom
- ME4 = Equal opportunities for all students to give opinions
- ME5 = Equal opportunities for all students to ask questions
- ME6 = Equal opportunities for all students to show their competences
- ME7 = Equal opportunities for all students to use their own regional language of communication in free time
- ME8 = Code of conduct applying to all students to appreciate the respective regional languages
- ME9 = Equal opportunities for all students to use international language in teaching and learning processes
- ME10 = Equal opportunities for all students to use their own regional language of communication in free time
- ME11 = Equal opportunities for all students to use international language in teaching and learning processes
- ME12 = Equal opportunities for all students to use international language in teaching and learning processes

Fig. 2 The structural model

b. Discussions

Table 1 presents that the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) reached 0.077 showing that the model of multicultural education practices is a good fit. Normed Fit Index (NFI) arrived at 0.825, indicating that the model offered is a good fit. Incremental Fit Index (IFI) attained 0.878, stating that the model is a good fit. Comparative Fit Index (CFI) gained 0.875 suggesting that the model provided is a good fit. Based on the SEM measurement result of this research, the multicultural education practices model for higher education students in the covid-19 pandemic era hypothesized in this research is a fit model.

Table 2 presents the measurement model test of the observed variables. Table 2 reveals that significantly positive associations between campus climate and hidden curriculum, teaching styles and strategies, communication language, and elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students on multicultural education practices were 0.898, 0.879, 1.002, and 0.904, respectively. The observed variables of equality of teacher behaviour, equal tolerance culture, and equal opportunities given to all students related to participation in classroom are significantly related to campus climate and hidden curriculum ensuring equal opportunities for all students of 0.325, 0.642, and 0.607, respectively. Sub-indicators of equal opportunities for all students to give opinions, to ask questions, and to show their competences are significantly associated with teaching styles and strategies ensuring equal opportunities for all students reaching 0.681, 0.556, and 0.578, respectively. Sub indicators of equal opportunities for all students to use their own regional language of communication in free time, code of conduct applying to all students to appreciate the respective regional languages, and equal opportunities for all students to use international language in teaching and learning process have a significant relationship with language of communication ensuring equal opportunities for all students achieving 0.317, 0.437, and 0.423. Sub indicators of equal opportunities for all students to join the school program, to participate in class discussion, and to give recommendation for campus have a significant relationship with elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students achieving 0.677, 0.730, and 0.461. This result is consistent with the study that found that multicultural education practices can improve sympathy and positive feeling toward others (Quinto-Pozos, Martinez, Suarez, & Zech, 2018; Warshaw, Crume, & Perez, 2020).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This research proposes an empirical model for multicultural education practices. Indicators including u campus climate and hidden curriculum, teaching styles and strategies, communication language, and elements of participation ensuring equal opportunities for all students stimulate multicultural education practices. The limitation of this study is that the scope only involves students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia. It is recommended for further researcher to include all students in the Province of Jakarta in Indonesia.

References

- Brown, J., C. & Livstrom, I., C. (2020). Secondary science teachers' pedagogical design capacities for multicultural curriculum design. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 31(8), 821-840.
- Edwita, Safitri, D., Maksum, A., Yunaz, H., Marini, A., and Muda, I. (2019). The effect of student cultural enculturation on student art appreciation. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(4), 469-478.
- Fahrurrozi, Safitri, D., Marini, A., Wahyudi, A. (2019). Model of students' learning styles at elementary school. *Opcion*, 35(29), 1402-1417.
- Freire, J., A. & Valdez, V., E. (2021). The holistic analysis of multicultural teaching framework: Capturing teachers' pauses and their hybrid and fluid multicultural practices. *International Journal of Multicultural Education*, 23(2), 127-144.
- Kaban, S., Sakmal, J., Auliaty, Y., Marini, A., and Wahyudi, A. (2019). Model of creative thinking skills for elementary school students. *International Journal of Control and Automation*, 12(4), 70-76.
- Maksum, A., Safitri, D., Ibrahim, N., Marini, A., and Wahyudi, A. (2019). Self-efficacy model for elementary school students: Case in Indonesia. *Opcion*, 35(88), 851-865.
- Maksum, A., Safitri, D., Ibrahim, N., Marini, A., and Wahyudi, A. (2020). Impact of self-leadership on student critical thinking. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 12(3), 284-304.
- Marini, A., Maksum, A., Edwita, E., Satibi, O., and Kaban, S. (2019). School management on the basis of character building in teaching learning process. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1402, 1-6.
- Marini, A., Zulela, M., S., Maksum, A., Satibi, O., Yarmi, G., and Wahyudi, A. (2019). Model of character building for elementary school students. *International Journal of Control and Automation*, 12(4), 01-10.
- Omar, N., Noh, M., A., C., Hamzah, M., I., & Majid, L., A. (2015). Multicultural education practice in Malaysia. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 174, 1941-1948.
- Quinto-Pozos, D., Martinez, M., Suarez, A., & Zech, R. (2018). Beyond bilingual interpreting: Interpreter education considering a growing linguistic diversity in the U.S. *International Journal of Interpreter Education*, 10(1), 46-59.

- Rihatno, T., Safitri, D., Nuraini, S., Marini, A., Putra, ZE., F., F., Wahyudi, A. (2020). The development of character education model using stop motion animation for elementary school students in Indonesia. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(8s), 103-109
- Safitri, D., Umasih, Ibrahim, N., Sujarwo, Marini, A., and Wahyudi, A. (2019). Ecotourism model in Jakarta. *Opcion*, 35(21), 791-812
- Safitri, D., Umasih, Yunaz, H., Marini, A., and Wahyudi, A. (2019). Model of environmental education. *International Journal of Control and Automation*, 12(4), 49-55
- Warshaw, J., S., Crume, P., Perez, H., P. (2020). Impact of service-learning on Latinx college students engaged in intervention services for the deaf: Building multicultural competence. *International Journal of Multicultural Education*, 22(3), 50-75
- Wibowo, U. B., Marini, A., Safitri, D., Utami N. C. M., and Wahyudi, A. (2019). Managing school to develop students' creative thinking skills in the context of their learning styles. *Opcion*, 35(21), 1093-1106

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